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Deliverable D5.1 – Report on co-production of capacity building resources

WP5 – Capacity building for stakeholder engagement

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Partners short names / Legal name

APRE	Agenzia per la Promozione della Ricerca Europea
ATC	Athens Technology Center S.A.
FONDAZIONE CIMA	Centro Internazionale di Monitoraggio Ambientale – Fondazione CIMA
FONDAZIONE CMCC	Fondazione Centro Euro-Mediterraneo sui Cambiamenti Climatici
ECSA	Verein Der Europaeischen Buergerwissenschaften – ECSA E.v.
IBE	Fundación Ibercivis
ICLEI EURO	ICLEI European Secretariat GMBH (ICLEI EUROPASEKRETARIAT GMBH)
IIASA	Internationales Institut fuer Angewandte Systemanalyse
SEI OX	Stockholm Environment Institute, Oxford Office Limited
SEI TAL	Sihtasutus Stockholmi Keskkonnainstituudi Tallinna Keskus
UNIGE	Univeriste de Geneve

Abbreviation and Acronyms

Acronym	Description
ACH	AGORA Community Hub
CBR	Capacity building resource
D	Deliverable
ECCA	European Climate Change Adaptation
EDMO	European Digital Media Observatory
EU	European Union
EURESFO	European Urban Resilience Forum
ICT	Information and communication technology
RAST	Regional Adaptation Support Tool
SOCIOECOS	Climate Change, Sustainability and Socio-ecological Practices Conference
T	Task
TG	Target Group
TUUWI	TU-Umwelt initiative
UN	United Nations

WP	Work package
WWF	World Wildlife Fund

1. Executive Summary

Using co-production and capacity building resources can amplify engagement and adaptation activities by empowering citizens, encouraging inclusivity, and promoting bottom-up communication between scientists, authorities, and local communities. Given the increased impacts of climate change within Europe, the Adaptation AGORA project has collected, identified, and applied selected capacity building resources (CBRs) within its Pilot region events. The Adaptation AGORA Project aims to develop CBRs in the context of co-production activities to provide a deeper understanding of these systems in the context of climate change adaptation.

This deliverable (D) reports on the work undertaken as part of Task 5.1 (T5.1) within Work Package 5 (WP5) of the Adaptation AGORA Project. WP5 focuses on capacity building for stakeholder engagement within the four Pilot regions of Malmö (Sweden), the Aragón Region (Spain), the City of Rome (Italy), and the City of Dresden (Germany). T5.1 builds from the resources and knowledge produced from other Project Ts and WPs, as well as leverages other projects and existing resources, to develop CBRs produced from the results of the Pilot co-production events. The CBRs collected and analysed by T1.3 and the challenges identified by WP2 served as the basis for the citizen engagement methodologies selected and used within the T5.1 events. T1.3 specifically identified capacity building methods that were utilised in T5.1 activities, such as focusing on bottom-up communication and addressing vulnerable groups. Efforts from WP2 highlighted climate risk vulnerabilities and adaptation gaps within the Pilot regions, as well as citizen engagement methods, both of which aided in developing capacity building events of T5.1. Building from the challenges identified in WP2 allowed the T5.1 events to address the specific needs of the Pilot regions, which furthered the empowerment of the participants. Furthermore, the projects identified through T1.3 were compiled into a database showcasing their resources related to climate adaptation, citizen science, capacity building, and citizen engagement. Results from other projects and existing resources provided a blueprint from which the T5.1 activities were built, maximising the potential and cost-effectiveness of the events.

The Pilot events provided the opportunity to engage with local stakeholders and citizens in the co-production process to develop CBRs in the areas of climate adaptation and disinformation campaigns. Other engagement events organised by the Adaptation AGORA Project, including the Inception Workshops and focus groups, provided additional insights into the specific climate impacts of each Pilot region, which allowed the T5.1 activities to address the specific needs of each Pilot region. Combining a co-production approach with citizen engagement activities produced a participatory environment in each of the events that highlighted community vulnerabilities and produced insights into adaptation solutions for each Pilot region. For instance, the Inception Workshops highlighted effective citizen science techniques and adaptation gaps in local communities within the Pilot regions, like the lack of engagement with rural communities in the Aragon Pilot. The observations from the Inception Workshops and other Project activities furthered the development of T5.1, maximising the capacity of the events and ultimately empowering the participants and Pilot regions in climate adaptation and disinformation.

Following the work carried out by T5.1, the results will contribute to the development of the Digital AGORA, serving as content for the Digital Academy modules and the Digital Handbook. T5.1 also enhanced the reach of the Project and fostered engagement of the Project Digital Tools. By the time D5.1 is published, D5.2 – *Report on online cross-regional peer-to-peer activities* – will also have been published.

2. Introduction: the co-production process of capacity building resources

2.1. Background on capacity building and co-production

There has been a growing interest in enhancing citizen capacity and using co-production techniques to facilitate effective community engagement and climate adaptation. When backed by regulations, economic instruments, and capacity building, adaptation initiatives are more likely to have a larger impact (Ulibarri et al., 2022). Capacity building, as defined by the European Union (EU)-funded Climate-ADAPT Project, is “the process by which individuals or organisations obtain, improve, or retain the skills, knowledge, tools, equipment, or other resources to do their work competently” (Climate-ADAPT, 2020). In climate adaptation activities, capacity building can aid in increasing the knowledge of participants as well as the researchers. Furthermore, capacity building can shift the perspectives of participants, highlighting power dynamics, vulnerabilities, or inequalities that were not previously known (Blake et al., 2021).

CBRs can be used in a variety of ways. Most commonly in climate adaptation, they are applied through workshops, training exercises, and community engagement initiatives (Ziervogel et al., 2022). CBRs used in climate adaptation activities have been shown to incentivise individuals to adopt more strategies into their daily life (Ulibarri et al., 2022). While capacity building has increased in use in adaptation initiatives, research on effective CBRs can be vague and difficult to implement in engagement and co-production scenarios. Co-production refers to the collaboration of researchers, practitioners, and the public in delivering public services (Jaspers & Steen, 2020; van der Graaf et al., 2021). Using co-production in engagement activities can improve the creation of public outcomes, making them more responsive and inclusive and by maximising the use of resources (Jaspers & Steen, 2020). Co-production has also been seen as to overcome top-down communication barriers and promote inclusive engagement that emphasises local knowledge, bottom-up actions, and knowledge sharing (Visconti, 2023).

In the Adaptation AGORA Project Pilot regions, citizen engagement, capacity building, and co-production have been found to enhance climate adaptation initiatives. A study by Ballester and Mott Lacroix (2016) found that in the Ebro Basin in Spain, social awareness was able to increase the adaptive capacity of citizens and influence the design and development of the participatory process, concluding that the ability of participation processes depends upon the implementation of engagement methods. Furthermore, a look into co-production methodologies in East Naples was shown to potentially enhance ground-level resilience and increase engagement among

stakeholders (Visconti, 2023). Alternatively, a lack of engagement, capacity building, and co-production methods can hinder climate adaptation efforts. Qualitative interviews in Sweden revealed weakened capacity by the local municipality administration that hindered more integrated climate adaptation, underscoring the importance of community engagement and local knowledge sharing (Storbjörk & Hedrén, 2011).

The Adaptation AGORA project thus focuses heavily on capacity building in co-production and citizen engagement spaces. T5.1 utilised capacity building resources to engage with participants in the Pilot regions and expand their knowledge in climate change adaptation and climate disinformation. Furthermore, T5.1 employed the Regional Adaptation Support Tool (RAST), developed by the EU Mission to Adapt, as a guide for organizing the events in the Pilot regions (EU Mission on Adaptation). **Figure 1** showcases the RAST Model and an overview of its steps.

Figure 1. RAST Model produced by the EU Mission on Adaptation.

This model was designed to aid local and regional authorities with climate change adaptation strategies and plans (Climate-ADAPT). The RAST model is comprised of six steps:

Step 1 involves preparing the ground for adaptation and is broken down into 5 sub-steps, as shown by **Figure 2**. This step is designed to help users assemble and organize the essential components for an effective start to the adaptation process and set the stage for future activities. This step was carried out in WPs 1 and 2 through knowledge collection, inception workshops and focus groups. WP1 laid the groundwork for T5.1 activities by identifying essential CBRs. T1.3 identified effective CBRs that were applied in the Pilot events. Efforts from WP2, the inception workshops, co-creation workshops, and focus groups also contributed to the preparation of the climate adaptation and disinformation activities in T5.1. These activities brought together 8 different target audiences in

each of the Pilot regions, identifying essential stakeholders and engagement methodologies that would kickstart the activities of T5.1.

Figure 2. RAST Model Step 1 process.

Step 2 comprises assessing climate risks and vulnerabilities. Understanding climate risks and vulnerabilities is essential in providing comprehensive and effective local and regional adaptation. This step is divided into 4 sub-steps displayed in **Figure 3**.

This step creates a guideline for understanding the principal risks and vulnerabilities of the intended stakeholders and helps determine the priorities of the adaptation initiative. The inception workshops carried out by T2.1 implemented Step 2 of the RAST Model. These workshops identified the adaptation vulnerabilities and gaps in the Pilot regions, furthering the development of the capacity building events in T5.1.

In Step 3, users identify adaptation options and take inspiration from effective adaptation practices. When identifying adaptation options, it is important to keep in mind the key risks and adaptation objective created in Step 2. Users should also consider a diverse range of adaptation options, ensure that these options align with other policies and initiatives, compile factsheets for each option, and reference case studies for inspiration and insight. Building off previously identified local climate vulnerabilities from the European Environment Agency, CIMA, and the CMCC Foundation, the inception workshops of T2.1, and other project results, T5.1 identified effective engagement methodologies to incorporate into the Pilot events.

Figure 3. RAST Model Step 2 process.

Step 4 involves assessing and selecting the adaptation options. In this step, users will evaluate the adaptation options identified in Step 3 and will establish a framework for selecting which measures to employ in their adaptation plan. Stakeholder engagement is key within this step. Users should engage stakeholders in both the criteria and selection process, as this will ensure that risks and vulnerabilities are being integrated as well as promote interest in the adaptation plan. Following the identification of engagement and capacity building methodologies from T1.3, WP2, and other existing resources, T5.1 created capacity building kits, which included presentations on the areas of climate adaptation and disinformation. These kits served as the outline for the T5.1 events.

In Step 5, the selected adaptation policies and actions are implemented. This can be done by using individual adaptation plans or by integrating them into broader organizational plans. Step 5 is achieved through 4 sub-steps. **Figure 4** displays the Step 5 process.

The resources produced during this step are essential in helping drive organizational change, foster collaboration, influence stakeholders, secure funding, and guide the monitoring, evaluating, and learning efforts. Communication and engagement are also crucial during this step. Effective and long-term engagement will foster trust, build productive relationships, and promote communal approval of adaptation initiatives. This step is seen with the execution of the T5.1 capacity building events. Each Pilot event applied the resources and knowledge collected from other WPs and existing resources and projects, amplifying the potential of each event.

Figure 4. RAST Model Step 5 process.

Finally, this last step involves monitoring, evaluating, and learning. Step 6 helps ensure the adaptation plan stays on track and delivers the intended results and is illustrated by **Figure 5**. Step 6 promotes learning from the successes and failures identified during this process. It should be noted that while Monitoring, Evaluating, and Learning is assigned to this step, it should be applied throughout the RAST process. The insights derived from this step will improve future adaptation policies and should be shared internally and externally to enhance the collective understanding and progress of adaptation initiatives.

Each of the RAST Model steps were implemented within the Pilot regions during the stakeholder engagement events of T5.1. The steps helped us apply the most effective adaptation and engagement options during the Pilot events. These include identifying climate adaptation information that specifically targets the vulnerabilities of the Pilot regions, disinformation strategies that help citizens combat misinformation (EFFECT Strategy, Denial Machine), and engagement tools that promote knowledge sharing and foster dialogue among participants (surveys, group activities, storytelling, etc.). D5.1 serves as the monitoring, evaluating, and learning step (Step 6) of the RAST Model, where we evaluate the activities of T5.1 and share the insights gathered. By utilizing the existing knowledge developed from other WPs and citizen science projects, and executing the RAST model provided by the Mission, Adaptation AGORA was able to develop and expand upon existing capacity building resources based on the events organized by T5.1.

Figure 5. RAST Model Step 6 process.

2.2. Project and deliverable overview

This is a deliverable of the Adaptation AGORA Project – A Gathering place to co-design and co-create adaptation funded by the EU’s Horizon Europe initiatives within the Mission on Adaptation to Climate Change. Adaptation AGORA aims to strengthen European climate resilience by fostering best practices in engaging citizens and stakeholders in climate adaptation and transformative processes. WP5 – *capacity building for stakeholder engagement* – has two main objectives:

- Support interregional peer learning and knowledge exchange within and between regions and communities to co-design and deploy citizen science initiatives for capacity building on climate change adaptation and countering climate disinformation.
- Foster the “think global, act local” concept through continual knowledge sharing to promote cross-regional and cross-pollination possibilities and to produce appropriate materials to raise awareness and increase the resilience of citizens against climate disinformation.

WP5 aims to create a legacy of capacity building resources from the events and inputs of WP5 and other Adaptation AGORA WPs. Each T derived from WP5 plays into the legacy of CBRs. T5.1 highlights the capacity building events held in the project Pilot regions. T5.2 showcases the peer-to-peer learning events organized by WP5. Along with organising capacity building events, T5.1 also works with tasks 5.2 and 5.3 to harmonize the co-creation of CBRs in the form of presentations, videos, webinars, and other materials. Lastly, T5.4 works on connecting the dots on CBRs through a one-pager info-sheet and making connections to the AGORA Community Hub (ACH) and the Adaptation AGORA Zenodo community. Developing the relationship between each of the WP5 tasks will provide a set of tools to empower users to learn about climate change risks and employ capacity building resources for climate adaptation.

This deliverable will address T5.1 – *Co-produce capacity building resources* – of the Adaptation AGORA Project. This task aims to co-design and deploy citizen science initiatives for capacity building in the two areas of “climate change adaptation” and “climate disinformation”, and to foster a “think global act local” mindset through continuous knowledge exchange between different Project tasks and WPs and from existing resources and projects.

Additionally, the co-production of resources has also been shaped through the interaction and active feedback with the stakeholders directly participating in the Adaptation AGORA Pilots, as well as the “followers”. This target audience is defined as organizations that are not operating in the geographic regions where the Adaptation AGORA Pilots are, yet they are also actively engaged in the climate change adaptation processes of co-creation, co-design, and co-production. This includes decision-makers in other regions in the same countries, such as the City of Salerno, in Italy, as well as in other European countries for instance the City of Almeida, in Portugal. This has helped in shaping and defining the outreach of the abovementioned “think global act local” mentality, together with the shared vulnerabilities and gaps that were identified within WP2. **Figure 6** showcases the knowledge exchange achieved in T5.1.

Figure 6. WP5 knowledge exchange.

The inputs for T5.1 include T1.3, challenges identified in WP2, and existing resources and other projects. These inputs aided in the collection, assessment, and selection of CBRs, engagement techniques, and citizen science methodologies that were utilized in the capacity building Pilot events. They also highlighted gaps in research and vulnerabilities of the Pilot regions and identified

the Target Groups (TG) that were directly addressed in the T5.1 events. Following T5.1, the outputs from the Pilot events will contribute to the development of T5.4 – *Translating insights and lessons learned on capacity building* – and content for the Digital Adaptation AGORA tools (T2.2, T3.3, T3.4, T3.5) and the Digital Handbook (T6.2).

Applying the RAST Model, T5.1 was built from the work carried out from T1.3, WP2, and existing resources and projects. T1.3 served as a prerequisite task, identifying the CBRs that were to be applied in the T5.1 capacity building events. The challenges derived from WP2 (T2.1 and 2.2) highlighted adaptation and disinformation vulnerabilities and identified the Target Groups (TGs) in the Pilot regions. T5.1 was divided into five activities. The RAST Model was further applied within these activities to enhance the development of T5.1 **Figure 7** displays how the RAST Model was replicated within the T5.1 activities. A description of the activities is as follows:

- *Activity A5.1.1:* Identify the activities to be carried out within the Task, preparation of Implementation Plan for the Task, and resolution of key issues (e.g. in-person, online, hybrid events)
- *Activity A5.1.2:* Identify main TGs per Pilot region (twin activity to Task 2.1) and first timeline of events (Milestone = 1 event before December 2023)
- *Activity A5.1.3:* Inspect the capacity building resources identified in T1.3 and selected based on challenges and needs identified in WP2
- *Activity A5.1.4:* Capacity building initiatives (for climate adaptation and tackling disinformation) adapted to the needs of local communities and participating stakeholders
- *Activity A5.1.5:* Draft and consolidate version of the Deliverable

T5.1 will co-design and deploy citizen science initiatives for capacity building in the two key areas of “climate change adaptation” and “tackling disinformation campaigns on climate change”. This task serves as the basis for the academies developed in Tasks 3.4 and 3.5 and has the pre-required activity performed in T1.3. Findings from challenges addressed in WP2 (Tasks 2.1 and 2.2) will aid in the selection of citizen science initiatives used in WP5. The events carried out in this task will strengthen the network of communities and regions joining the Mission, with at least two events in each of the Pilot regions, 1 event focusing on the two key areas of T5.1. The initiatives used in T5.1 will also leverage resources, tools, guidelines, and other resources from previous citizen science projects, such as I-CHANGE, NO2NoThanks, and Changegame. These resources, along with the outcomes from T2.4, will be adapted to the needs of the local communities and participating stakeholders to maximise transformational change on climate adaptation.

Figure 7. Application of the RAST Model during the T5.1 activities.

By utilising the resources gathered in T1.3 and the challenges identified in WP2 as a form of guidelines, T5.1 was able to select, implement, and shape capacity building techniques to the needs of the local communities and stakeholders participating in the Pilot events. The outputs from T5.1 will provide contents for the Academies that are developed in T3.4 and T3.5, as well as T5.4 and the Digital Handbook (T6.2). T5.1, therefore, serves as the beginning step in creating the CBR legacy of WP5.

First, we will highlight synergies and cross-fertilizations with other Adaptation AGORA WPs in the production of CBRs. By learning and building on the CBRs from other WPs, we were able to apply these resources to the activities organised in T5.1. Secondly, we will describe the stakeholder engagement activities held in the four Pilot regions in the areas of “climate change adaptation” and “climate disinformation”. These activities incorporated resources from other WPs and produced valuable insights into co-production and capacity building for climate adaptation. Lastly, we will showcase how Adaptation AGORA was able to utilize existing CBRs and leverage other projects.

3. Cross-fertilisation with other WPs

3.1. Addressing the challenges and needs identified in the Pilot regions.

The inception workshops provided a crucial platform for engaging stakeholders in discussions about climate change adaptation. The diversity of participants reflected the complexity of climate adaptation, reinforcing the need for holistic approaches that integrate multiple perspectives. By emphasising a bottom-up flow of information, the Adaptation AGORA team fostered an inclusive environment where stakeholders could contribute their expertise, ensuring that local needs and challenges were at the core of discussions. **Table 1** showcases the Inception Workshops conducted by the Adaptation AGORA project.

Table 1. List of Inception workshops

Date	Location	Participants
16 November 2023	Dresden	24
19 December 2023	Valderrobres - Aragón Region	8
24 October 2023	Zaragoza - Aragón Region	18
9 November 2023	Rome	34
12 September 2023	Malmö	11

A recurring theme across the workshops was the lack of knowledge and public awareness regarding climate adaptation. Many participants acknowledged that insufficient access to information, coupled with limited social support, hinders effective adaptation strategies. Additionally, gaps in adaptive capacity were evident, particularly in areas such as socioeconomic inequalities, inadequate infrastructure, and governance inefficiencies. In many cases, weak coordination between local, regional, and national governments led to inconsistent policies and unclear divisions of responsibility. This lack of coherence often results in a reactive rather than proactive approach to climate adaptation, with short-term measures prioritised over comprehensive, long-term planning.

The discussions also underscored significant regional disparities in climate vulnerabilities. While all four pilot regions are experiencing increasing temperatures, water scarcity, and extreme weather events, their specific challenges vary. For instance, Malmö and Dresden, not historically accustomed to high temperatures, are struggling with the impact of heatwaves on workforce productivity and public health. Meanwhile, water dependency emerged as a pressing issue in Dresden, Rome, and Zaragoza, highlighting the need for more resilient water management strategies.

Table 2. Inception Workshop Sweden

General info	Stakeholders	Main objective(s)
<p><i>Where:</i> University of Malmö <i>When:</i> 12th of September '23 <i>Participants:</i> 11</p>	<p>[TG2] Academia [TG3] Governments and Decision-Makers / Authorities [TG4] Civil Society [TG6] Private sector [TG8] Consortium Partners</p>	<p>Climate adaptation and social vulnerability, specifically focusing on heatwaves in Malmö. The goal was to lay the groundwork for future collaboration and identify key issues related to heatwave impacts and vulnerable groups.</p>

Beyond environmental vulnerabilities, the workshops highlighted broader social and structural issues that exacerbate climate risks. Ageing populations, internal migration trends (rural depopulation and urban population growth), and economic inequalities all contribute to the complexity of adaptation efforts. Buildings and infrastructure are often ill-equipped to withstand climate impacts, further complicating the response to environmental threats.

Each workshop had a distinct focus shaped by local priorities. In Malmö, discussions revolved around heatwaves, while in Valderrobres, the emphasis was on forest management and fire prevention. Despite these variations, the structure of the workshops remained consistent, with initial presentations followed by breakout discussions that encouraged stakeholder-driven problem-solving. The only exception was in Dresden, where a single group discussion format was used.

Table 3. Inception Workshop n.1 Spain

General info	Stakeholders	Main objective(s)
<p><i>Where:</i> Aquarium of Zaragoza <i>When:</i> 24th of October '23 <i>Participants:</i> 18</p>	<p>[TG2] Researchers and experts [TG3] Political groups [TG4] Environmental groups [TG5] Citizens [TG6] Private sector</p>	<p>Adaptation to climate change in Aragon region. Development of participatory dynamics and tools, promoting the sharing of ideas, values, emotions and opinions. Participatory methodologies to identify existing gaps in the region's adaptive capacity.</p>

One of the most striking insights from the workshops was the difficulty of engaging rural stakeholders, particularly in Aragón. Factors such as an aging population, depopulation, and weak inter-community connections make it challenging to involve rural communities in adaptation planning. This issue underscores the need for more targeted outreach strategies to ensure that rural voices are not overlooked in climate policy discussions.

While climate adaptation policies are gaining importance across Europe, their local implementation remains a critical challenge. The workshops reaffirmed findings from the literature, particularly regarding the difficulties in communication, public engagement, and the unequal distribution of climate adaptation resources. Climate change has been shown to deepen social and economic inequalities, an issue that was clearly reflected in the Pilot regions. However, despite increasing attention to the psychological impacts of climate change, such as eco-anxiety, this topic did not emerge as a significant concern in stakeholder discussions.

Table 4. Inception workshop n. 2 Spain

General info	Stakeholders	Main objective(s)
<p><i>Where:</i> Headquarters of the Matarraña region in Valderrobres (Teruel)</p> <p><i>When:</i> 19th of December '23</p> <p><i>Participants:</i> 8</p>	<p>[TG2] Academy [TG3] Governments and Decision-Makers [TG5] Citizens</p>	<p>Development of collaborative strategies for the sustainable management and protection of private and municipal forests in the Matarraña region, focusing on fire prevention and the conservation of natural resources in the context of climate change.</p>

Ultimately, the insights gathered from these workshops will play a key role in shaping future climate adaptation strategies. The Adaptation AGORA project remains committed to fostering dialogue and collaboration among stakeholders to co-design and co-create effective adaptation measures tailored to the needs of the pilot regions.

These initiatives had a focus on the co-design and deployment of citizen science initiatives to build capacity in two strategic areas: “Climate Change Adaptation” and “Combating Disinformation Campaigns on Climate Change”. The aim was to promote the “think global, act local” principle through continuous knowledge exchange. The activities served as foundation for the development of the Academies planned in Tasks 3.4 and 3.5 and contingent upon the prior completion of T1.3.

Table 5. Inception workshop Rome

General info	Stakeholders	Main objective(s)
<p>Where: “Casa delle Tecnologie Emergenti”, Rome When: 9th of November ‘23 Participants: 34</p>	<p>[TG2] Academia [TG3] Governments and Decision-Makers / Authorities [TG4] Civil Society [TG6] Investors / Private Sector [TG8] Consortium Partners</p>	<p>Discussion about adaptation to the expected impacts of climate change in relation to a plurality of sectors identified among the key areas most vulnerable identified in the process of the preparation of Climate Change Adaptation Strategy. Definition of the main socio-economic, structural, and environmental vulnerabilities and the main needs and criticalities of the territory adaptive capacity</p>

Table 6. Inception workshop Germany

General info	Stakeholders	Main objective(s)
<p>Where: citizens' lab (Bürgerlabor), Dresden When: 16th of November ‘23 Participants: 24</p>	<p>TG2] Academia [TG3] Governments and Decision-Makers / Authorities [TG4] Civil Society [TG6] Investors / Private Sector</p>	<p>Identification of vulnerability and risk drivers and gaps in relation to local adaptive capacity through an assessment of local susceptibilities to the expected climate hazards. Alignment of adaptation priorities and requirements with the needs of local communities (soft adaptation measure).</p>

Citizen science initiatives were selected based on the challenges and needs identified in WP2 (T2.1 and T2.2). These initiatives contributed to strengthening the network of communities and regions engaged in the Mission by organizing a minimum of **two events** per Pilot area, one focused on Climate Adaptation, the other one focused on Climate Disinformation, across the four Pilots, resulting in at least eight events overall. The initiatives have utilized resources, tools, and guidelines from previous citizen science projects (e.g., *The News Evaluator*, *The Food Waste Experiment*,

NO2NoThanks, I-CHANGE, Changegame), ensuring cost-efficient replication. The resources and insights developed, along with the outcomes from T2.4, will be tailored to the specific needs of local communities and stakeholders to maximize transformational change in climate adaptation efforts.

3.2. Building on existing capacity building resources

WP1 aims to identify existing practices and resources related to citizen engagement. In T1.3, actions were taken to compile and analyze CBRs for climate change adaptation and fighting disinformation campaigns. The resources were found from projects funded by the European Commission under Horizon 2020 and Horizon Europe. The CBRs analyzed in T1.3 were specifically aimed at enhancing knowledge, awareness, and appropriate behavioral change of citizens in relation to climate change adaptation and climate disinformation. Resources found included training materials, digital tools, networking platforms, reports, books, and multimedia materials, such as videos and podcasts.

The analysis revealed major gaps and needs in CBRs in the areas of climate change adaptation and disinformation. Some of the most relevant included a lack of attention to vulnerable populations and critical areas of climate change, a need for multiple forms of media, a lack of focus on the later stages of adaptation, a lack of accessibility, and a lack of EU-funded projects and initiatives focusing on climate disinformation. Based on the gaps identified, recommendations were provided for future capacity building and adaptation activities:

- Create CBRs in multiple languages to increase accessibility and reach broader audiences.
- Address vulnerable or least represented groups, including citizens and the private sector, through a bottom-up and co-production approach to gain an understanding of their unique challenges and risks and to empower them during capacity building and adaptation events.
- Engage citizens and stakeholders throughout the entire adaptation and capacity building process.
- Incorporate practical steps to properly prepare participants against climate-related hazards and disinformation.

The insights gathered from T1.3 efforts were further developed into various datasets published on the Project online channels and on the Adaptation AGORA Zenodo Community, an open-source repository for EU Project outputs. Publishing the insights in an open-source format allows for the replication of these efforts and the application of the resources, furthering the legacy of the Adaptation AGORA Project.

T1.3 served as a pre-requirement activity upon which T5.1 is to be built from. The recommendations from D1.3 – *Report on capacity building resources on climate change adaptation and disinformation campaigns* – paired with the challenges identified from WP2, served as guidelines for the development of the events and workshops carried out in T5.1. The gaps identified in D1.3 were directly addressed in the T5.1 capacity building events and other WP5 outputs. T5.1 events focused heavily on bottom-up and co-production approaches for engagement in adaptation and disinformation. The events also emphasized solutions-based communication, aiming to build the

capacity of participants to combat disinformation and empower them to adopt climate adaptation initiatives.

Furthermore, resources from other projects gathered by T1.3 were compiled into a master database that was also utilized for T5.1 activities. This database showcased other EU projects and any resources relating to citizen science, capacity building, and climate adaptation they provided. These resources from other projects furthered the development of T5.1 activities by providing research and methodologies for capacity building and climate adaptation. A condensed version of this database can be seen in Section 5.

The collected CBRs from T1.3 also feed into the development of T5.4, translating insights and lessons learned on capacity building. T5.4 directly addresses one of the gaps identified in T1.3: a lack of CBRs in local languages. Additionally, T1.3 also supports the content of the Digital AGORA, highlighting gaps in research areas and vulnerabilities in the Pilot regions that are addressed in the content of the Academy modules and the mobile App question bank.

4. The capacity building events in the Adaptation AGORA Pilot regions

The Adaptation AGORA Project has held many activities within its Pilot regions of Spain, Germany, Rome, and Sweden across the different WPs that aim at enhancing the capacity of citizens in climate adaptation and disinformation. Focus groups and co-creation workshops organised by WP2 were held in each of the Pilot regions and explored co-designing soft adaptation solutions among different target audiences, like workers, school students, and elderly populations. The peer-learning workshops carried out by WP1 and WP6 focused on implementing engagement methodologies, combining the work of WP2, WP3, and WP4 to showcase the various efforts of engagement within the Project. WP worked to co-produce innovative solutions through interviews and surveys that expanded the reach of the Project and gathered essential data from practitioners and policy makers on climate resilience.

Along with the planned WPs activities, the Project also attended various events that further expanded the capacity of the Project and provided additional insights into climate adaptation and disinformation. The Project partner IBERCIVIS (IBE) attended a course on scientific journalism in Spain, where they presented the Project and conducted interviews on climate change and disinformation. Another Project partner, ECSA, attended a workshop in Dresden, Germany to share the Project and the relevance of citizen science in climate adaptation.

WP5 relates to the work of WP1 and WP3 to tackle climate disinformation. The efforts from WP1 feed into the activities of WP5, and outputs from both WP1 and WP5 serve as content for WP2 in the Mobile app and WP3 in the Digital Academy against climate change disinformation. Both WP3 and WP5 work to co-develop an integrated discussion and learning space. The capacity building events from T5.1 allow various target audiences to share their knowledge and experiences with climate adaptation and disinformation, while WP3 works to create an online space for learning and discussion through the Digital AGORA.

The efforts and activities organised from each of the Project WPs provided deepened understanding and valuable data on climate adaptation, citizen engagement, and disinformation that aided WP5 efforts. Furthermore, the events from the Project promoted capacity building tools, making them available for a larger number of stakeholders, and expanded the potential audience for WP5 activities. The link between WP5 and other Project WPs strengthens the initiatives of both WP5 and the Project as a whole, broadening the knowledge on climate adaptation and disinformation and enriching the Project’s reach in the Pilot regions.

As part of the T5.1 activities, multiple events were held in the Project Pilot regions with different events focusing on the topics of climate adaptation and disinformation. By implementing the RAST Model and building from the resources and knowledge gained in T1.3 and WP2, the T5.1 events were able to tailor capacity building and co-production methods to the target audiences, maximizing the potential of each event. **Table 7** displays an overview of the Pilot events carried out by T5.1. The following sections will review the events held in each Pilot region, one focusing on adaptation and one focusing on disinformation, and showcase the outputs and any lessons learned from each event. While T5.1 organised multiple capacity building events within the Pilot regions, we will focus only on the two most effective events per Pilot region that produced significant insights into the Project and major contributions to capacity building.

Table 7. Overview of T5.1 Capacity building events focused on climate adaptation and combating disinformation campaigns.

Pilot	Climate Adaptation		Disinformation Campaigns	
	Event Type	# of Participants	Event Type	# of Participants
Rome	In-person event with university students	>100 participants	Climate, News, and Fake-News: Navigating the climate crisis between science and information	10-15 participants
Malmö	Malmö in the Making	45 participants	Disinformation and Climate Adaptation Webinar	49 participants
Aragón	“Future Scenarios and Adaptation Strategies” Workshop	Approx. 30 participants	“How to Combat Misinformation about Climate Change” Workshop	10 participants

Dresden	“Heat Stress and Heat Protection in Healthcare” Workshop	23 participants	Disinformation and Climate Adaptation Webinar	49 participants
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4.1. Italy

4.1.1. *Climate Adaptation Event: “Capacity building with architecture undergraduates”*

22/04/2024

This activity was designed to empower university students in Rome by addressing climate change adaptation through a multidimensional and interdisciplinary approach. Drawing on content from the initial workshop held in Rome, as well as showcasing Project tools currently under development, the capacity building session brought together students, primarily from the faculties of architecture and economics, for a multidisciplinary training aligned with the United Nations (UN) Agenda 2030 and its Sustainable Development Goals. More than 100 students participated in the event. University professors gave a brief introduction, followed by a keynote on sustainable urban mobility in Rome, with a particular focus on bike lanes and the evaluation of related challenges and solutions.

Professors Andrea Filpa and Chiara Tonelli introduced the Adaptation AGORA project team from CMCC, including Paola Mercogliano (project coordinator), Alfredo Reder, Marianna Adinolfi, and Arianna Acierno. Paola Mercogliano presented the Project’s objectives, placing Adaptation AGORA within the broader context of CMCC's research initiatives. To engage the audience, the session began with an interactive Mentimeter survey exploring key issues related to climate change and adaptation, and to gather initial insights from the students. Paola then delivered a foundational lecture on climate change and adaptation, providing essential background to support the discussions that followed. Alfredo Reder offered an in-depth look into the Adaptation AGORA project, highlighting the Italian Pilot's efforts to involve stakeholders in identifying and addressing local adaptation challenges.

Figure 8. Climate change and Adaptation event Italy

He detailed the participatory process and Adaptation AGORA's contribution to shaping Rome's adaptation strategy. Marianna Adinolfi and Arianna Acierno introduced two of Adaptation AGORA's digital tools: the Academy on Disinformation and the Academy on Climate Data. This demonstration aimed to showcase tangible project outcomes and to gather student feedback on the tools' design and functionality. To conclude, a survey was distributed to collect additional perspectives on local adaptation gaps and to gauge the level of youth engagement with climate adaptation in Rome. The session ended with a final discussion and Q&A segment, encouraging active participation and reflection.

4.1.2. Tacking Disinformation Event: "Climate, News and Fake-News: Navigating the climate crisis between science and information"

The Italian Pilot conducted various events on disinformation, the first of them took place in Rome, hosted at the World Wildlife Fund (WWF) venue (via Po 25/a Roma) with approximately 40 participants, open to the general public, involving journalists and non-governmental organisations. To widen the audience, the event coupled in person and online participation in hybrid mode, via zoom platform. The workshop was an opportunity to discuss the topic of climate disinformation in the framework of the objectives and the methodologies of the Adaptation Agora project.

Professor Cook, one of the major experts on disinformation, opened the workshop with an introduction on the topic and the latest developments of his studies on this subject. Then followed by a presentation of the Adaptation AGORA Project and its focus and outputs on disinformation. Climate discussion forcefully enters people's lives, into the administrations of our cities, into the political sphere. For this reason, information has a decisive role both for those who produce it and for those who use and share it. Understanding the way in which social media uses scientific information on a complex topic such as climate change, is essential to better understand how

climate disinformation affects our perception of climate change. The workshop tackled the solutions to effectively address climate disinformation and understand the climate crisis.

With international experts and insights into the perspectives of new technologies, the meeting offered an analysis of the state of the art and a series of tools that allow to distinguish fake news from correct information, based on scientific grounds. The objective was to provide the audience with the appropriate tools to select sources of information within the huge amount offered by the traditional media and the digital universe.

The event was in Italian, and a translation was provided in English for the Italian contents alongside with a translation in Italian for John Cook's speech. The workshop went on with a discussion on methodologies, suggestions and ideas to improve the Projects' results and concluded with the interview of John Cook, link below.

List of speakers:

John Cook - Melbourne Centre for Behaviour Change at the University of Melbourne, founder of SkepticalScience.com.

Introductory keynote speech.

Paola Mercogliano - CMCC, Director of the "Regional Models and geo-Hydrological impacts" Research Unit, and coordinator of the Adaptation AGORA project.

Antonello Pasini - CNR, Institute on air pollution.

Monia Azzalini - Pavia Observatory for the analysis of information on the climate crisis in Italian media.

Mariagrazia Midulla - WWF Italia, responsible for the Climate and Energy Unit.

Edoardo Zanchini - Municipality of Rome, Director of the Climate Office.

Riccardo Luna - Green&Blue, Repubblica

Moderator: Mauro Buonocore - CMCC, Head of Communication and Media Office.

<https://www.youtube.com/watch?v=VZ2Xwll0SAc>

4.2. Spain

4.2.1. Climate Adaptation Event: “Future Scenarios and Adaptation Strategies”

The first capacity building event in the Spanish Pilot was a workshop designed to deepen participants understanding of the climate impacts affecting their region and co-design adaptation strategies to combat these impacts. Held on April 27th, 2024, in Calamocha, Aragón, WP5 organized this climate adaptation event targeted towards students aged 16 to 18 and some of their teachers. The event was divided into two main activities: a brainstorming activity and discussion. The timeline of the event is as follows:

Participants were welcomed by Adaptation AGORA members, and an introduction of the event was provided. During the introduction, Project members explained the reasoning for the event and introduced the Adaptation AGORA Project, as well as provided a brief introduction on climate adaptation. Participants were provided information on climate change, its impacts, and adaptation and resilience. Following this short introduction, the event facilitators then summarized the activities.

The first activity involved brainstorming climate change impacts and future scenarios. Participants were given two prompts to answer; the first, “How do you think climate change affects you and your family”, and the second “Imagine your town or city in 10 years, what would you do to adapt it to the effects of climate change?”. These questions were written on two large sheets of paper and participants wrote their responses on post-its, placing them under the respective prompt. This allowed for anonymity and promoted participants to write multiple ideas for each prompt. **Figure 9** shows the participants completing this first activity.

Figure 9. Participants from Spanish Pilot climate adaptation event responding to the prompts of the first activity.

Following the first activity, the event facilitators shared the ideas that were produced, and a debate arose among the participants. The facilitators and participants discussed the different responses and any potential alternatives to the proposed ideas. Once this discussion concluded, the facilitators ended the event by thanking the participants and encouraging them to participate in the Adaptation AGORA Project. Participants that were over the age of 18 were also given a survey that asked for more in-depth understanding of the climate change impacts on their region. This survey was also given during over Adaptation AGORA events in the Spanish Pilot. These survey results have been translated into a paper under T4.2 of the Adaptation AGORA Project.

The results from this first capacity building event in the Spanish Pilot saw varied responses on climate change impacts based on participants' geographical area. For instance, participants from the Canary Islands showed greater concern towards climate change impacts on tourism and poor water management for natural conservation, while participants from the rural south of Spain were more concerned with impacts on farming and depopulation. Overall, participants had a pessimistic view on climate change impacts in Spain. For the future adaptation scenarios, participants highlighted adapting housing for increased energy savings, producing climate shelters, planting crops that are more adapted to increased temperatures, reducing plastic use, and increasing the awareness on the conservation of the natural environment.

This capacity building event fostered effective engagement from the participants, allowing them to reflect upon their individual and shared experiences of climate change and gain a deeper understanding of how climate change affects where they live. Furthermore, co-producing

adaptation scenarios not only empowered the participants, but it also provided meaningful insights into local climate experiences and vulnerabilities within the Pilot region and built trust between citizens and the Adaptation AGORA Project.

4.2.2. Tackling Disinformation Event: “How to Combat Misinformation about Climate Change”

Following the climate adaptation event, a disinformation workshop was held in the Spanish Pilot on October 24th, 2024. The event was organized by the Adaptation AGORA partner IBE, using their national project AULaCheck, and Verificat. AULaCheck is a media literacy and critical thinking project organized by IBE that aims to increase the ability of citizens to distinguish between fake news and reliable information. Verificat is a non-profit organization in Spain aimed at fighting against disinformation and manipulation of the internet. The goal of this workshop was to share strategies to detect misinformation about climate change. The event was held online to increase the number of participants. **Figure 10** displays the information of the event that was shared in the Pilot region and through Adaptation AGORA networks.

Figure 10. Promotion for the disinformation event in the Spanish Pilot.

Adaptation AGORA and Verificat began this workshop by welcoming participants and introducing the facilitating projects. Along with the Desfake Project, Verificat then explained the process of verifying information found on social media and political discourses. It was highlighted that using

Media and Information Literacy encompasses the competency to engage with information and knowledge in a critical and responsible manner. They further explained the principal narrative of denialism in terms of climate change, touching on the social, economic, and environmental consequences. The presentation continued with EFECT Strategy, which can be applied to identify and deny climate disinformation. The strategy can be seen in **Figure 11**.

The first step of the strategy, False Experts, refers to those who claim to be knowledgeable or “experts” on a certain topic, but who, in actuality, have low or non-existent levels of knowledge. Logical Fallacies are arguments in which the initial premises do not logically lead to the conclusion.

Figure 11. The EFECT Strategy used to identify disinformation campaigns.

An example of this was given to the participants: “The climate has changed naturally in the past, so what is happening now must be natural”. Impossible Expectations refers to demanding impossible levels of precision from scientists before acting on the problem. This can be seen in statements like “Scientists cannot even predict next week’s weather. How are they going to know the climate of the next century?”. Cherry Picking occurs when one only focuses on information that aligns with their argument and ignores information that opposes it. Lastly, Conspiracy Theories are secret plans that aim to pursue malicious and self-interested goals.

After the presentation on disinformation and strategies from Verificat and Desfake, participants were put in breakout rooms for an activity to perform the EFECT strategy. The instructor gave one true fact on climate change and asked participants to create climate misinformation using the fact and applying the EFECT strategy. Once each group finished, they received a misinformation that was created by a different group, and were tasked to determine which part of the EFECT strategy was used, which anti-climate narrative it responds to, and what reality the misinformation is trying to hide. Each group then presented their answers. The instructor suggested the Cranky Uncle game, which uses cartoons and critical thinking to fight misinformation. At the end of the workshop, participants shared their experiences with disinformation in high schools where they worked and in their day-to-day interactions and a debate ensued between the participants and facilitators.

This event armed the participants with strategies to combat climate disinformation through a presentation and group activity, and the results provided understanding into climate disinformation within high schools and in local communities.

4.3. Germany

4.3.1. *Climate Adaptation Event: “Heat Stress and Heat Protection in Healthcare”.*

The capacity building event of the German pilot was conducted on March 25th, 2025, with a focus on “Nursing at the Municipal Hospital Dresden” - Location: Staff Restaurant, 1st Floor in Building V (Municipal Hospital Dresden, Neustadt / Trachau Location).

With the aim of empowering local communities, particularly healthcare workers, to better understand and adapt to the challenges of climate change, the capacity building event centered on the theme of climate adaptation. The event took a novel approach by prioritizing the health and working conditions of nursing staff during extreme heat events, rather than the more common focus on patient vulnerability alone. Held in the pilot region of Dresden, the workshop brought together key stakeholders from the private sector, government, and civil society, including representatives from the Municipal Hospital Dresden, the Dresden Office for Health and Prevention, and the civil society initiative Health for Future. This multi-stakeholder engagement was underpinned by sociocratic principles, promoting shared decision-making and empowering all voices. The workshop pursued several interlinked objectives and thematic focus:

- To build the capacity of nursing staff in dealing with extreme heat.
- To deepen understanding of local climate change impacts and corresponding adaptation strategies.
- To reflect on and build upon findings from earlier focus group discussions with healthcare workers.
- To explore the development and implementation of a heat protection plan at the Municipal Hospital Dresden.

By shifting attention to how extreme heat affects healthcare workers, and how these effects, in turn, influence patient care, the event filled a critical gap in climate-health dialogues. The collaborative organization of the workshop was a key factor in its making. Stakeholders from different domains worked together to create an inclusive environment for dialogue. The guiding sociocracy framework ensured that each participating group had equal standing and input, leading to a more democratic, responsive process. This governance model was particularly effective in a context where cross-sector coordination is vital. The workshop content was structured around three expert presentations:

1. Climate Change and Local Impacts in Dresden: This presentation contextualized the workshop by explaining climate trends in Dresden, the urban heat island effect, and local adaptation initiatives, including infrastructure improvements and public resources like the “Heat Platform” and “Refill Stations.”

2. Extreme Heat and Health Impacts: Focusing on the direct and indirect health effects of heat, especially for vulnerable groups and healthcare workers, this session emphasized the risks of dehydration, cardiovascular strain, and workplace exposure.
3. Heat Protection in Healthcare: Practical strategies for protecting healthcare workers were shared, with measures categorized across awareness, individual behavior, organizational changes, and policy development. The introduction of a formal Heat Protection Plan was a central proposal.

A central feature of the workshop was the collaborative discussion following the presentation of previous focus group findings. Participants co-developed a set of concrete, actionable solutions across five thematic areas such as

- Organizational and Structural Measures: Including the provision of fresh food and water, scheduling adjustments, and handling heat-sensitive medications.
- Clothing and Equipment: Proposals included breathable uniforms and pilot programs for cooling garments.
- Training and Education: Calls were made for certified e-learning, cross-departmental training, and the integration of national guidance.
- Policy and Participation: Emphasis was placed on participatory planning, staff agreements, and clear operational guidelines.
- Communication and Awareness: Ideas ranged from better patient information to internal reporting tools for heat stress conditions.

Several themes emerged during open discussions that extended the core learnings:

- Heat Protection Officers: The idea of appointing dedicated personnel was discussed, with a consensus that heat protection should be a collective responsibility embedded across roles and departments.
- Communication Culture: Participants called for a workplace culture that fosters mutual respect, open dialogue, and shared authority—what some termed “loving authority.” Such a culture is critical for implementing climate adaptation in a high-stress environment like healthcare.
- Addressing Resistance: The strategy of working initially with committed staff while gradually engaging sceptical colleagues was viewed as a realistic pathway to institutional change.
- Feasibility of Technical Solutions: While mobile air conditioning units were suggested, practical and financial constraints led to the conclusion that such solutions are not currently viable.

The workshop demonstrated the value of interdisciplinary collaboration and participatory methods in addressing climate challenges in healthcare. It provided a platform not only for knowledge transfer but also for co-creation and empowerment, particularly among nursing staff. While many actionable ideas were proposed, the event also highlighted ongoing challenges, including resource limitations, institutional inertia, and the need for cultural change. Going forward, sustaining

momentum will require continuous engagement, transparent communication, and supportive policy environments. By placing healthcare workers at the center of climate resilience efforts, the workshop exemplified a forward-looking approach to adaptation, one that is grounded in both practical measures and the lived realities of those on the front lines of care.

Musterhitzeschutzplan für Krankenhäuser

1. Maßnahmen zur Vorbereitung auf den Sommer

Organisation	Verantwortliche Struktur in einem Krankenhaus benennen, die für Hitzeschutz und die Umsetzung des Hitzeschutzplanes verantwortlich ist	
	Einen für die einzelne Einrichtung spezifischen Hitzeschutzplan erstellen (Planung der Arbeitsabläufe der einzelnen Abteilungen in der Klinik während der Hitzeperioden unter Berücksichtigung der vorhandenen Möglichkeiten der Gebäudetechnik)	
Organisatorische Schulung	Den für das Krankenhaus bestehenden Hitzeschutzplan unter den Mitarbeitenden bekanntmachen	●
Medizinische Schulung	Fortbildungsmaßnahmen für Mitarbeitende zum Thema hitzebedingte Erkrankungen durchführen	●
	Fortbildungsmaßnahmen für Mitarbeitende zum Thema Anpassung von medikamentösen Therapien unter Hitzebedingungen durchführen	●
Technische Hitzeschutzmaßnahmen	Hitzerelevanten Ist-Bauzustand der Gebäude sowie auch der Umgebung (Begrünungskonzept) erfassen	●
	Überbrückungskonzept für Extremereignisse/Notfälle wie Stromknappheit/-ausfall prüfen bzw. entwickeln (Sicherstellung der Stromversorgung der Raumlufteinrichtungen)	
	Sonnenschutzkonzept prüfen bzw. entwickeln (Außenbereiche/Innenbereiche - Zimmer)	●
	Kühle Zonen/Erholungsbereiche (Cooling zones) erfassen	
	Kühlungs-/Klimatisierungskonzept unter Berücksichtigung der Krankenhaushygiene entwickeln (lang- und kurzfristige Maßnahmen für Patient:innen und Mitarbeitende)	●
	Temperatur und Luftfeuchtigkeit der Innenräume messen und dokumentieren	
Personalplanung	Ärztlichen und pflegerischen Personalmehrbedarf bei Personalressourcenplanung für Maßnahmen in Warnstufe 1 und 2 berücksichtigen, Vertretungspersonal einrichten	

2. Maßnahmen während der Sommermonate

Lagerung wärmeempfindlicher Medikamente und Materialien	Medikamente generell in verschattbaren Räumen in Metallschränken aufbewahren, um die für die Lagerung angegebenen Temperaturbereiche einzuhalten	●
	Medikamentenkühlschränke sind mit Thermometern ausgestattet, es erfolgen regelmäßige, protokollierte Kontrollen der Kühlschranktemperaturen	
	Die Versorgungslager für Materialien befinden sich in fensterlosen Räumen	

Aktionsbündnis Hitzeschutz Berlin – eine Initiative der ÄKB, SenWGP und KLUG e.V.
Stand: Januar 2023, Version 3

Figure 12. Climate Adaptation Germany

4.3.2. Tackling Disinformation Event: “Disinformation and Climate Adaptation”

The final T5.1 capacity building event was a webinar on climate disinformation and climate adaptation. This was held online via Zoom on April 23rd, 2025. The event was co-organized with the student-led organization TUUWI, formed by a group of students from all disciplines and semesters

who are committed to climate justice from the Technical University of Dresden. The goal of this webinar was to build awareness among university students of climate disinformation and understand strategies to combat it. This event was unique as it involved students from both the German and Swedish Pilots, bringing these two regions together under a shared interest in understanding climate disinformation and adaptation.

The webinar began with brief welcome by a representative of TUUWI, who introduced the speakers and gave an outline of the event agenda. Paula Gori, from the European Digital Media Observatory (EDMO), then gave a presentation on climate disinformation. She began by defining climate disinformation and misinformation, providing real-world examples, such as a post claiming a speech by Greta Thunberg resulted in immense amounts of trash left behind, when in reality the trash resulted from a concert. Paula then described the denial machine, which details the different messages of climate disinformation. **Figure 13** displays the denial machine described during Paula’s presentation. The goal of these disinformation narratives is to plant doubt of climate change in the public’s mind. Paula highlighted the critical role that human behaviour plays into the spread of disinformation, emphasizing how tactics can exploit one’s natural cause-and-effect thinking, perceptions, and emotions. People’s tendency to simplify complex issues and seek reassurance can make it particularly challenging to engage with topics like climate change.

Climate change denialism

DENIALS

- No warming is taking place (trend denial)
- CC is not anthropogenic (attribution denial)
- CC has no negative impact on humans and on the environment (impact denial)
- There is no consensus among scientists on human causes (consensus denial)
- Green solutions are equally polluting (solutions denial)

ACTORS/DENIAL

- governments
- think tanks, foundations
- industry
- media
- the public

> denial machine: create doubt

- About the reality of CC
- About the urgency of CC
- About the credentials of scientists
- About solutions

* Bjornberg et al, Climate and environmental science denial: A review of the scientific literature published in 1990–2015, Journal of climate change production. 2017

EU SCHOOL OF TRANSNATIONAL GOVERNANCE • Treen et al, Online misinformation about climate change, WIREs Climate Change, 2020

This project has received funding from the European Union

Figure 13. Screenshot of Paula Gori’s presentation on climate change denialism.

Paula then presented various solutions to identify and counteract climate disinformation, underscoring the critical role communication plays. Paula’s presentation prompted questions from the attendees, inquiring how individuals without a scientific background can approach scientific literature and identify disinformation, and how to foster trust in scientists and institutions,

especially among those who are sceptical or distrustful. In response, Gori reiterated the importance of listening and understanding and stressed the need to consider cultural contexts in communication. Gori also noted that those with a limited understanding of climate change are more vulnerable to disinformation.

Following Gori's presentation, members from Adaptation AGORA presented the Project and its Digital Tools. Participants raised questions regarding the Mobile App, specifically asking for the rationale behind the app and if updates to the app have been planned. The webinar was recorded and can be viewed on the Adaptation AGORA YouTube channel. https://youtu.be/fzMGou7g-18?si=uaW7Xj_0Ooj3sXlg

This final capacity building event engaged students from both the German and Swedish Pilots, raising awareness on climate disinformation and adaptation. Participants showed a strong desire in understanding how to combat climate disinformation and how to foster trust between the scientific community and those who are sceptical of climate change. The results from this event revealed a common theme, the need for improving the dissemination of research and expanding scientific communication to audiences outside academia and experts.

4.4. Sweden

4.4.1. *Climate Adaptation Event: "Malmö in the Making"*

Sweden has experienced increased heatwaves as a result of climate change. To address this impact, the City of Malmö has begun assessing the social vulnerability of heatwaves. *Malmö in the Making* is a public program that explores the meaning of public space, architecture and culture for the Swedish citizens and how they can foster more collaborative urban development. As part of this program, the City of Malmö organized a climate adaptation event on September 12th, 2023, to explore adaptation as a layer of urban justice. This event served as the starting point for discussion on how adaptation strategies can be designed to vulnerable communities and those with the largest need for resilience initiatives.

As part of T5.1 activities, Adaptation AGORA participated in this public event. The Stockholm Environment Institute (SEI) presented their previous work on social vulnerability to raise awareness on social vulnerabilities, climate change, and adaptation. This event engaged with members of civil society, academia, and local government authorities to discuss climate adaptation initiatives that can increase community resilience.

During the event, SEI presented an overview of their development of social vulnerability index of flooding risks in Halmstad, and how these insights can be used in local urban planning and policy to support more just climate adaptation, which can be seen in **Figure 14**. Following this, local officials from Malmö's environmental department provided an overview of Malmö City's climate adaptation strategies and how greening interventions can provide several ecological and social co-benefits:

- Better health outcomes
- Increased biodiversity

- Micro-climate regulation
- Social meeting places that strengthen community bonds

A potential greening initiative to harness these co-benefits was then presented. To obtain co-benefits from trees, Malmö has developed a 3-30-300 strategy that would promote equal access to greenspace, and the city had already begun extensive tree mapping to assess the health status of this green infrastructure. At the time of this event, there were however, major legal barriers on both national and local governmental levels, as no regulatory frameworks took heatwaves into account.

Figure 14. Malmö in the Making event - SEI presentation on social vulnerabilities.

After the presentation from the city, a district nurse shared his insights and experiences of working directly with elderly citizens in care homes, who were vulnerable to heatwaves. He stressed the importance of institutional factors that affect the capacity to respond to heat stressors, such as temporary workers during the summer months and difficulties discerning the responsibilities in terms of caretakers' living environments.

Following the nurse's speech, Växtverket, a local nonprofit, shared their insights from the project Naturmolnet. This project collaborated with the local community, involving children, local artists, and neighbours, to transform a vacant lot into a community garden and gathering space. A researcher from Lund University then discussed the opportunities and barriers of climate adaptation in urban development, emphasizing the importance of taking a multi-scale approach to green infrastructure solutions, as the outcomes and co-benefits vary at different scales.

The event ended with a panel discussion with the various speakers. This promoted dialogue between the speakers and event participants on how these emerging initiatives can be supported

to create a more just and climate-resilient Malmö.

This first capacity building event in the Swedish Pilot showcased the potential of community engagement, showcasing the value of multi-sector participation within climate adaptation. This event gathered insights from various parts of the community, from citizens to government representatives, building trust between these sectors and paving the way for inclusive climate adaptation within the Swedish Pilot.

4.4.2. Tackling Disinformation Event: “Disinformation and Climate Adaptation”

The final T5.1 capacity building event was a webinar on climate disinformation and climate adaptation. This was held online via Zoom on April 23rd, 2025. The event was co-organized with the student-led organization TUUWI formed by a group of students from all disciplines and semesters who are committed to climate justice, from the Technical University of Dresden. The goal of this webinar was to build awareness among university students of climate disinformation and understand strategies to combat it. This event was unique as it involved students from both the German and Swedish Pilots, bringing these two regions together under a shared interest in understanding climate disinformation and adaptation.

The webinar began with a brief welcome from a representative of TUUWI, who introduced the speakers and gave an outline of the event agenda. Paula Gori, from the European Digital Media Observatory (EDMO), then gave a presentation on climate disinformation. She began by defining climate disinformation and misinformation, providing real-world examples, such as a post claiming a speech by Greta Thunberg resulted in immense amounts of trash left behind, when in reality the trash resulted from a concert. Paula then described the denial machine, which details the different messages of climate disinformation. **Figure 13** displays the denial machine described during Paula’s presentation. The goal of these disinformation narratives is to plant doubt of climate change in the public’s mind. Paula highlighted the critical role that human behaviour plays into the spread of disinformation, emphasizing how tactics can exploit one’s natural cause-and-effect thinking, perceptions, and emotions. People’s tendency to simplify complex issues and seek reassurance can make it particularly challenging to engage with topics like climate change.

Paula then presented various solutions to identify and counteract climate disinformation, underscoring the critical role communication plays. Paula’s presentation prompted questions from the attendees, inquiring how individuals without a scientific background can approach scientific literature and identify disinformation, and how to foster trust in scientists and institutions, especially among those who are skeptical or distrustful. In response, Gori reiterated the importance of listening and understanding and stressed the need to consider cultural contexts in communication. Gori also noted that those with a limited understanding of climate change are more vulnerable to disinformation.

Following Gori’s presentation, members from Adaptation AGORA presented the Project and its Digital Tools. Participants raised questions regarding the Mobile App, specifically asking for the rationale behind the app and if updates to the app have been planned. The webinar was recorded

and can be viewed on the Adaptation AGORA YouTube channel. https://youtu.be/fzMGou7g-18?si=uaW7Xj_0Ooi3sXlg

This final capacity building event engaged students from both the German and Swedish Pilots, raising awareness on climate disinformation and adaptation. Participants showed a strong desire in understanding how to combat climate disinformation and how to foster trust between the scientific community and those who are skeptical of climate change. The results from this event revealed a common theme, the need for improving the dissemination of research and expanding scientific communication to audiences outside academia and experts.

5. The use of existing capacity building resources, leveraging on other projects

A major aspect of the Adaptation AGORA Project is enhancing the capacity of citizens in the Pilot regions in the areas of climate adaptation and disinformation, and efforts to achieve this are seen throughout the different WPs. Along with the activities performed in WP5, the Project has held numerous capacity building activities across the Pilot regions, promoting the Project tools and expanding the Project's reach in both the Pilot regions and the larger European region. In many of these activities, we share insights from the Adaptation AGORA Project, our digital tools, and any lessons learned from the activities performed across multiple forms of media dissemination. Adaptation AGORA has joined numerous webinars, like the MIP4Adapt webinar series in 2024 and the RESIST Digital Transition in Climate Change Adaptation event earlier this year, to present the Project and share the ICTs. In person events, like the SCIENCE US Bootcamp and the EURESFO Conference, allowed the Project to host workshops on citizen engagement for climate adaptation and showcase how the Digital Tools can be utilised by citizen engagement initiatives and stakeholders.

On April 9th, 2025, the Adaptation AGORA Project held a joint webinar with the CLIMAS Project that aimed to share project experiences and lessons learned from implementing participatory approaches to foster public involvement. Like Adaptation AGORA, the CLIMAS Project also focuses on co-creation, co-production, co-design, and co-implementation of adaptation actions. During this event, the CLIMAS Project shared the outcomes from their Climate Assemblies held in Catalunya, Spain, Riga, Latvia, and Edermünde, Germany. The Climate Assemblies organized by CLIMAS showcased valuable and effective engagement methods, including workshops and citizen science activities that emphasized local knowledge, bottom-up engagement and the co-production of adaptation strategies. The webinar highlighted the importance of citizen engagement and the potential replication of these participatory models across regions. The Adaptation AGORA Project has also established a collaboration with the RESIST Project, which aims to enhance the resiliency of European regions to climate change. This collaboration further extends the reach of our Project outside of the Pilot regions, thus promoting the dissemination of our results and digital tools and allowing us to gather additional insights into climate adaptation and disinformation.

Leveraging other projects and resources also served as stimulus for other Adaptation AGORA initiatives. T5.4, translating insights on capacity building, combined the resources compiled in T1.3 and addresses a major gap identified in the analysis: a lack of local languages. Furthermore, the insights from existing resources and projects serve as content for the Digital Adaptation AGORA tools by identifying gaps in research and vulnerabilities of the Pilot regions.

The capacity building activities organized in T5.1 utilized existing CBRs and leveraged other projects to develop effective and relevant information that would maximize the capacity of the Pilot events. Based on the work carried out in T1.3, **Table 8** was created to organize the resources developed from other projects. Using the resources from **Table 8**, T5.1 was able to benefit from the resources provided by other projects to identify successful citizen science, capacity building, citizen engagement, and climate adaptation methodologies. The analysis of the existing resources compiled in T1.3 also revealed vital gaps and vulnerabilities, which were then implemented in the T5.1 Pilot events. Understanding these gaps sparked the need for capacity building kits, which were created during T5.1, and include presentations on the areas of climate adaptation and disinformation that were used in the Pilot events and showcase the different knowledge and tools available to empower citizens, stakeholders, and academia. These capacity building kits are available on Adaptation AGORA SharePoint.

Table 8. Results from T1.3

List of multimedia materials from projects included in D1.3			
PROJECT	WEBSITE	DATES	RESOURCES
TERRIFICA	https://terrifica.eu/	Ended in 2022	<p>Citizen Science: The involvement of citizens in research through the lens of the TeRRIFICA project - YouTube BESNO LICE PRIRODE - YouTube https://youtu.be/F_MscIpyCwM?list=PLp6P8Wquyg9JwGaN9AYpFIhblFP-uA3kE https://youtu.be/VIRtCPxrvHk</p> <p>Policy Brief I: Citizen Participation Matters – Fostering Co-Creation for Climate Change Mitigation and Adaptation: https://terrifica.eu/wp-content/uploads/2021/03/TeRRIFICA_D5.1_Policy_Brief_I_2021-02-09_def.pdf</p> <p>Policy Brief II: Guidelines for establishing a co-creation-based open science framework</p> <p>The second TeRRIFICA Policy Brief contains recommendations for stakeholders involved in R&I projects: https://terrifica.eu/wp-content/uploads/2022/12/TeRRIFICA_D5.2_PolicyBrief-2-final.pdf</p> <p>Effective practices in community-academia research partnerships on climate change adaptation and mitigation – a Delphi study: https://terrifica.eu/wp-content/uploads/2020/07/Effective-practices-in-community%E2%80%93academia-research-partnerships-on-climate-change-adaption-and-mitigation.pdf</p>
GREENWIN	http://green-win-project.eu/	01/09/2015 – 31/12/2018	<p>Booklet Greenwin Narratives: https://www.greenpolicyplatform.org/sites/default/files/downloads/resource/181112_Booklet_Green-Win_two-sided.pdf</p> <p>Governance of social dilemmas in climate change adaptation: https://green-win-project.eu/resource/governance-social-dilemmas-climate-change-adaptation</p> <p>Energy Poverty Eradication and Climate Resilient Livelihoods through Win-Win Solutions: https://www.greenpolicyplatform.org/sites/default/files/downloads/resource/Energy%20Poverty%20Eradication%20and%20Climate%20Resilient%20Livelihoods%20through%20Win-Win%20Solutions.pdf</p>
RESCCUE	https://www.agbar.es/	01/05/2016 – 30/11/2020	Materials only in Spanish.

<p>UNALAB</p>	<p>https://unalab.eu/en</p>	<p>01/06-2017 – 30/11/2022</p>	<p>EVALUATING THE IMPACT OF NATURE-BASED SOLUTIONS: A HANDBOOK FOR PRACTITIONERS: https://unalab.eu/system/files/2021-06/evaluating-impact-nature-based-solutions-handbook-practitioners2021-06-15.pdf HANDBOOK ON IMPLEMENTATION AND ADOPTION BARRIERS OF URBAN LIVING LABS DEVELOPING NATURE-BASED SOLUTIONS: https://unalab.eu/system/files/2021-09/handbook-implementation-and-adoption-barriers-urban-living-labs-developing-nature-based.pdf UNALAB NBS TECHNICAL HANDBOOK FACTSHEETS: https://unalab.eu/system/files/2022-11/unalab-nbs-technical-handbook-factsheets2022-11-17.pdf NBS INFOGRAPHIC: https://unalab.eu/system/files/2020-05/nbs-infographic2020-05-11.pdf UNALAB NBS BOOKLET: https://unalab.eu/system/files/2020-05/unalab-nbs-booklet2020-05-20.pdf</p>
<p>RETHINK ACTION</p>	<p>https://rethinkaction.eu/</p>	<p>01/10/2021 – 30/09/2025</p>	<p>Video introduttivo del progetto: https://www.youtube.com/watch?v=rYh2doQyleg Profilo ig</p>
<p>REGILENCE</p>	<p>https://regilience.eu/</p>	<p>01/11/2021 – 31/10/2025</p>	<p>The REGILENCE self-assessment tool to spot risks of maladaptation:https://regilience.eu/wp-content/uploads/2023/12/REGILENCE-maladaptation-tool202311.pdf</p>
<p>ARSINOE</p>	<p>https://arsinoe-project.eu/</p>	<p>01/10/2021-30/09/2025</p>	<p>Policy Brief: https://arsinoe-project.eu/securstorage/2023/01/ARSINOE-Policy-brief.pdf https://www.youtube.com/watch?v=d00XhtPD3hw https://www.youtube.com/watch?v=VfU8jKvSnOQ</p>
<p>SINCERE</p>	<p>https://jpi-climate.eu/programme/sincere/</p>	<p>01/02/2018 – 31/01/2022</p>	<p>Science for policy – How to engage with policy makers? https://jpi-climate.eu/wp-content/uploads/2024/01/Policy-Brief-Session-3-Science-for-policy-How-to-engage-with-policy-makers.pdf</p>
<p>I-CHANGE</p>	<p>https://ichange-project.eu/</p>	<p>01/11/2021 – 30/04/2025</p>	<p>I-CHANGE video: Co-benefits of Climate Actions: Co-benefits of Climate Actions - YouTube I-CHANGE video: The most challenging Climate Change Impacts for Cities: https://youtu.be/DcnzsKcasnQ I-CHANGE video: Climate Change and the European Green Deal: Climate Change and the European Green Deal - YouTube</p>

REACHOUT	https://reachout-cities.eu/	01/10/2021 – 31/03/2025	Policy Brief: https://reachout-cities.eu/wp-content/uploads/2023/08/policybrief-nr1-Reachout-September-2023.pdf Pagina IG: https://www.instagram.com/reachout_cities?igsh=bDFpMWd1MDBnZjdo
HARMONIA	https://harmonia-project.eu/	01/06/2021 – 31/01/2025	HARMONIA Leaflet: https://harmonia-project.eu/wp-content/uploads/2022/07/Harmonia-leaflet.png Presentation video: Project Harmonia Presentation Video - English - YouTube
ECF4CLIM	https://www.ecf4clim.net/	01/10/2021 – 30/09/2025	Roadmap for sustainability education: https://www.ecf4clim.net/files/ugd/1088b3_0fb7cd80b475455c81fe8a904ec6aa37.pdf Baseline of Individual Competences: https://www.ecf4clim.net/files/ugd/1088b3_b266538d8b994d1cab30a338c8e8bde8.pdf Collective Competences for Sustainability: https://www.ecf4clim.net/files/ugd/1088b3_935637eaaaad4258a1baa81f983d5601.pdf Baseline assessment of the environmental performance: https://www.ecf4clim.net/files/ugd/1088b3_67c810731760403eaf53302bf40885cb.pdf
PSLifestyle	https://pslifestyle.eu/	01/10/2021 – 31/03/2025	Lifestyle Test Calculation Criteria - Finland (EN): https://pslifestyle.eu/fileadmin/user_upload/PSLifestyle_Test_Calculation_Criteria_Finland.pdf PSLifestyle video in English: PSLifestyle video in English - YouTube
CAPACITIES	https://dutpartnership.eu/capacities/	01/10/2022 – 30/09/2024	Interesting materials available in the downloads section: https://dutpartnership.eu/downloads/
LOCALISED	https://www.localised-project.eu/	01/10/2021 – 30/09/2025	Factsheet: https://www.localised-project.eu/wp-content/uploads/2024/05/LOCALISED_Gender-and-Diversity-monitoring-in-multidisciplinary-research-projects-D1.5_Apr24.pdf https://www.localised-project.eu/wp-content/uploads/2024/05/LOCALISED_SDG-Oriented-Indicators-for-SECAPs-definition-and-assessment-D5.1-flyer_Apr2024.pdf Why do smaller cities and regions need a climate change strategy in the first place?: Why do smaller cities

			and regions need a climate change strategy in the first place? - YouTube Interlinkages between Adaptation and Mitigation: Interlinkages between Adaptation and Mitigation - YouTube
AURORA	https://www.aurora-h2020.eu/	01/12/2021 – 31/05/2025	Policy Brief: Igniting University Communities: Building Strategies that Empower an Energy Transition through Solar Energy Communities: https://www.aurora-h2020.eu/wp-content/uploads/2024/04/2024-Solar-RRL-2023-Cristobal-Igniting-University-Communities-Building-Strategies-that-Empower-an-Energy-Transition.pdf
SOCIO-BEE	https://socio-bee.eu	01/10/2021 – 30/09/2024	Although topics differ from the ones of AGORA, the project makes available a tool-kit of capacity building materials which might be interesting for inspiration: https://socio-bee.eu/?page_id=1189
GreenSCENT	https://www.green-scent.eu/	01/01/2022 – 31/12/2024	GreenSCENT flyer 1: https://zenodo.org/records/10134974 GreenSCENT flyer 2: https://zenodo.org/records/10134646 GreenSCENT: we can all be changemakers! GreenSCENT: We Can All Be Changemakers! - YouTube GreenScent - Smart Citizen Education for a Green Future: https://ddd.uab.cat/record/256274?ln=ca
DivAirCity	https://divaircity.eu/	01/09/2021 – 31/08/2026	Visual leaflet of Engagement Principles, user scenarios, HMW's and city roadmaps: https://divaircity.eu/wp-content/uploads/2024/01/DivAirCity_Visualleaflet-1.pdf Pan European Contest: https://divaircity.eu/paneuropean-contest/
REAL_DEAL	https://www.realdeal.eu/	01/02/2022 – 31/01/2025	Policy Tool: (Deliverable and Policy Brief) https://assets.nationbuilder.com/theeuropeanmovement/pages/1740/attachments/original/1710233481/download-Policy_Tool_layout_v1.pdf?1710233481 The future of the European Green Deal: https://assets.nationbuilder.com/theeuropeanmovement/pages/1661/attachments/original/1699373883/download-Final_Real_Deal_Policy_Brief_EGD2.pdf?1699373883
PHOENIX	https://phoenix-horizon.eu/	01/02/2022 –	What does Digital tools for engagement mean?: https://youtu.be/yicceHUjupI

		31/07/20 25	
PERITIA	https://peritia-trust.eu/	01/02/20 20 - 31/05/20 23	Policy Brief: How Can Governments Build Trust in Science?: https://peritia-trust.eu/wp-content/uploads/2023/05/D3.4-Policy-brief-on-policies-for-better-science-advice_vsn-1.0.pdf Social Indicators of Trust - How We Trust (Scientific) Experts: https://youtu.be/JzmEe69tow?feature=shared

5.1. Collaboration with task 3.4 and 3.5

WP3 – *Living digital environment for knowledge co-production* – involves co-designing and implementing the Digital AGORA as well as producing a cross-sectoral framework for the co-evaluation of citizen and stakeholder engagement methodologies, which will be applied in WP2. T3.4 aims to build and maintain the Digital Academy on Climate Data Risks and Tools. This entails identifying, providing access to, and sharing guidance on how to use various open-source climate and risk data. This Academy empowers users to use technical reports and climate data and deepens their understanding on how to apply this data. T3.5 involves the Digital Academy on Climate Change Disinformation and strives to produce trustworthy information and resources on climate change and fact-checked information from credible sources.

The development and content of the Digital Academies will, in part, be based on the results from the activities carried out in T5.1. Furthermore, the survey conducted during the T5.1 capacity building event at Rome UniTre University showcased the Digital Academies and gathered feedback from the student participants. This feedback aided in the co-creation, co-development, and evaluation of the Digital Academies of T3.4 and T3.5 by providing valuable insights into the use and content of the Academies. T5.1 contributes to the activities of T3.4 and T3.5 by distinguishing existing best practices, activities, and experiences, identifying capacity building enablers and barriers, and providing exploitable CBRs that can be applied to the Academies. Much of the content in the Academies utilises the CBRs developed from T5.1 and it is expected that during the next events taking place during 2025 related to this specific task, stakeholders can provide valuable insights to continue enriching the online tools.

The results from T5.1 activities provided meaningful insights into climate impacts for each of the Pilot regions and identified vulnerabilities in some of the local communities. Many of the climate adaptation events involved the co-production of adaptation strategies, which encourages a bottom-up approach to climate adaptation. Understanding the climate impacts threatening the Pilot region communities offers specific areas of focus for T3.4 and the development of the Academy on Climate Data Risks and Tools. The climate disinformation events highlighted vital disinformation strategies to combat fake news and underlined a need for greater dissemination tools for climate information. These capacity building events also stressed the need to bridge the gap between science and local communities. The insights from these events provide essential content for the development of the Digital Academies, carried out by T3.4 and T3.5. The collaboration between these tasks (3.4, 3.5, and 5.1) maximises the potential of the Digital Academies and produces the most up-to-date and accurate resources for its users.

The connection between T5.1 and tasks 3.4 and 3.5 showcases the cyclical nature and interconnectedness of the Adaptation AGORA Project. **Figure 15** highlights the interconnectedness of T5.1 and the digital tools. The efforts of various WPs and tasks, such as the events organised by T5.1 and the Inception Workshops organised by WP2, aided in content development for the digital

tools by identifying significant climate adaptation gaps within the Pilot regions and useful CBRs. Furthermore, during the development of the Academies, they were displayed during T5.1 Pilot events and other Project activities, allowing participants to provide feedback on the Academies that aided in the development process, such as the survey conducted in the Rome Pilot at UniTre University. The Academies and Mobile app (WP2) were also tested during other dissemination activities, such as the ECCA 2023 and SOCIOS 2024 conferences, where feedback on the Modules helped determine the overall design and focus areas.

These events, both Project events and other dissemination activities, allowed the Project to gain feedback on the digital tools, furthering their development and enhancing their outreach capacity. For instance, from the feedback obtained from Pilot events, we learned that the Mobile app needed to be translated into different languages to increase its dissemination potential. Other activities helped narrow the focus and develop topics for the Digital Academies, specifically the Pilot events highlighted adaptation and disinformation gaps that are addressed in the Academies. Module 7 of the Academy on Climate Data Risks and Tools explores the social dimension of climate change, highlighting climate justice and social inequalities. The latter half of the module focuses on awareness-raising, engagement, and citizen-driven climate action, building on the themes of the T5.1 capacity building events.

In more recent activities, such as participating in the RESIST Project webinar on Digital Transition in Climate Change Adaptation, Adaptation AGORA has presented the Academies and other digital tools as CBRs. During the T5.1 and other Pilot events, the digital tools are also displayed as CBRs, and participants are encouraged to utilise them to amplify their knowledge and skills in climate adaptation and disinformation.

DIGITAL TOOLS FEEDBACK LOOP

Figure 15. Feedback loop between the digital tools and Adaptation AGORA activities.

The links between T5.1, other Project WPs, and the digital tools aids in the development of the Digital Academies. By showcasing the Digital Academies and obtaining feedback from the Pilot

regions, Project followers, and other stakeholders, we are able to further enrich the content, modify the topics, and adapt the Academies to be used as CBRs in future activities and enhance user experience.

6. Next steps

The results from T5.1 will be implemented into various Adaptation AGORA tasks, including the development of the Digital AGORA Academies (T3.4 and T3.5), the CBRs one-pager (T5.4), and content for the Digital Handbook (T6.2). Following the work carried out in T5.1, WP5 will continue with the development of future tasks. T5.3 involves strengthening citizen resilience against climate change disinformation and entails creating material based on inputs from T1.3, as well as T5.1. The aim of this task is to enhance media literacy and critical thinking skills by enhancing the capacity of citizens to distinguish between true facts and disinformation. The material from T5.3 will be incorporated into the Digital AGORA (T3.3, T3.4, and T2.2) outputs, as well as in the D5.3, which is scheduled for M32. T5.4 will synthesise all the CBRs generated from the other WP5 tasks and will feed this information into the Digital Handbook (T6.2) as well as through the Digital AGORA and other online channels. The information compiled through T5.4 will aid in building the legacy of the Adaptation AGORA Project and will represent a practical guidance that can be replicated to strengthen the capacity building of citizens and stakeholders.

T5.1 results will also feed into the content of the Digital Adaptation AGORA tools (T2.2, T3.3, T3.4, T3.5, and T6.2). Areas of vulnerabilities in climate adaptation and disinformation revealed during T5.1 events will be directly addressed in the Digital Adaptation AGORA tools, such as in the Question Bank of the Mobile App, in blog posts on the ACH, and in the lessons learned of the Digital Handbook. Integrating the results of T5.1 will allow the Digital Tools of the Project to target a variety of audiences, as they will specifically address the vulnerabilities of various demographics. Specifically, in the Digital Academy modules, results from T5.1 helped identify topics for content, such as the specific climate risks of the Pilot regions. In future Project efforts, T5.1 results will be integrated into the lessons learned of the Digital Handbook, allowing future projects to learn and grow from the experiences of T5.1 and replicate our efforts.

Along with T5.1 results, all the materials developed for and from the capacity building events and the resources developed by other projects relevant to the two topics of climate adaptation and disinformation will be collected and made available on the Adaptation AGORA Zenodo community, and other Project online channels, allowing for open-access use which promotes replication by other projects. This coincides with the activities of T5.4 and further feeds into the legacy beyond Adaptation AGORA by providing tools and resources to empower users in the areas of climate change adaptation and disinformation.

WP5 efforts have also resulted in additional events organised in the Pilot regions stemming from the T5.1 activities. In Malmö, there are plans to host and additional activity stemming from the results of the workshops held by WP2 and the capacity building events organised by WP5. Furthermore, an additional series of events were held in the Rome Pilot starting in October 2024.

Following T5.1, T5.2 - *Building up twinning AGORAs: online cross-regional peer-to-peer activities* – supports the development of successful collaboration in the field of climate adaptation. Through the online peer-to-peer event series, T5.2 aims to foster effective relationship building, conflict resolution, and communication processes among communities and local governments. This task is led by ICLEI, with CMCC serving as WP coordinator and contact with Rome Pilot, ECSA serving as contact with Dresden Pilot and aiding with the synergy between WP2, APRE supporting the communication of the T5.2 events, SEI-OX aiding in the integration of events within the Digital AGORA, and UNIGE aiding with the synergy of WP4. The final output of T5.2 (D5.2), is due in Month 34.

T5.3 - *Strengthen citizen resilience against climate change disinformation* – aims to raise awareness and increase the resilience of citizens against climate disinformation through the production of multimedia content (videos, articles, guides, etc.). Led by ATC, T5.3 is supported by CMCC, serving as WP coordinator and contributing the task activities with an emphasis on the Digital Academy against climate change disinformation modules, APRE, aiding in the organisation and development of material, IIASA, helping with material development, and IBE, contributing to all the tasks, emphasising the modules of the Digital Academy against climate change. The final output of T5.3 (D5.3), is due in Month 32.

Finally, T5.4 - *Connect the dots: translate insights and lessons learned on capacity building* – combines the findings and resources of the first three WP5 tasks to translate them into the languages of the Project Consortium. Ending in Month 34, the efforts of each of the WP5 tasks culminates with the output of T5.4, which will foster cross-regional learning and boost the replicability of the collected resources.

The complete timeline of WP5 is illustrated by **Figure 17** below. Each of the four WP5 tasks are essential to the achievement of WP5 and to the overall progress of the Adaptation AGORA Project.

Figure 17. Gantt chart depicting the timeline of all WP5 tasks.

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